
The Evolution and Genesis of Historical Dramas and the Emergence of Nationalism in Colonial Odisha

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Abstract:*This article delves into the development and evolution of historical dramas and nationalism in Colonial Odisha. It highlights key themes, prominent playwrights, and these dramas' cultural influence on Odia society. The discussion ranges from early performances to modern adaptations. Historical dramas in Odisha have served as entertainment and an educational medium, enlightening audiences about the region's rich heritage and significant historical events. A substantial contribution to the formation and propagation of Odia nationalism was made by historical dramas that were set in colonial Odisha. Not only do these stories illustrate the diverse cultural past of the area, but they also serve as a source of inspiration for the Odia people to develop a sense of shared identity. They do this by telling fascinating stories and bringing attention to the challenges and goals of the Odia community. It helps to cultivate a sense of solidarity and pride, which is necessary for the growth of nationalism.*

Keywords: Colonial, Drama, Folk, Jayadeva, Odisha, Khandagiri hills, Sanskrit etc.

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Introduction

A rich tradition of Sanskrit, folk, and western drama has evolved into modern theatre. The elephant cave inscriptions of Kharavel, carved in the second century BC, along with the historical stage of Indian theatre in the Khandagiri hills, indicate Odisha's deep-rooted theatrical heritage. Folklore-related information can be found in the Charyapadas, which date back to the 10th century. From the ninth to the eighteenth century, Sanskrit dramatic literature

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flourished in Odisha, with notable playwrights such as Murari Mishra, Vishwanath Kaviraj, Jivadev Acharya, Jayadeva, Kapilendra Dev, and Purusottam Dev contributing to the significant Sanskrit literary tradition. An example of Odia music can be found in the Sanskrit play *Parashuram Vijaya* by Kapilendra Dev (1435-66). Additionally, it is known that Ray Ramananda, a minister of Prataprudra Dev, constructed a particular stage in Puri to stage the drama, *Jagannatha Ballabh*.

The trend of *Gitinatya* (A form of performance that integrates dance, drama, and music) and popular dramas is likely derived from religious folklore, which includes various cultural events such as the *Harijanma* of Kalahandi District, *Rusyashringa Barana*, *Thakurani Yatra* of Koraput District, *Dhanu Yatra* of Sambalpur District, *Sitalsashthi Yatra*, *Lakshmi-Narayan Kali*, and *Sahiyat* of Puri District, as well as *Dhuli Danda* performed in various other districts. During the pre-composition era, performances such as *Ram Leela*, *Krishna Leela*, *Bharat Leela*, *Danda Nata*, and *Suanga* were created to entertain the general populace. These performances not only promoted traditional religious ideals but also addressed the romantic aspirations of the audience. Although aimed at the general public, these dramas often excluded depictions of everyday life and human experiences. The performances featured lyrical language and vivid acting, including the use of vulgar language, obscene remarks, and gestures by the actors to amuse the audience. This type of folk drama has persisted, albeit in a limited form, to the present day.

A Hermeneutical Analysis

The historical drama has emerged from contemporary literary and social trends, evolving within the framework of national consciousness. It is intrinsically linked to this national consciousness, examining historical drama relevant to Odisha's national identity development. However, Girija Shankar Ray's *Odia Natyakala* (1943) does not explore the evolution and development of historical dramas in Odisha. While drama is a common theme in Odia literature, there is a notable lack of critique and analysis addressing historical dramas. Works such as Kanhucharan Mishra's *Sahitya Samikhya* (1954), Birkishore Das's *Yuge Yuge Natya Sahitya* (1965) and its revised second edition (1975), Narayan Satapathy's *Odia*

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Nataka and Natyakra (1965), Ratnakar Chaini's *Udabhata Natya Parampara* (1972), and Hemant Kumar Das's *Odia Natakara Bikash Dhara* (1976) provide a general overview of drama but overlook the specific genre of historical drama. Although Niladri Bhushan Harichandan's *Odia Natakare Itihasra Pratidhwani* (1982) thoroughly examines historical dramas, it does not fully address the existing research gap. Additionally, five books authored by Bhagirathi Das, Madhusudan Pati, Janakiballbh Mohanty, Bhavagrahi Mishra, and Prasanna Kumar Mishra focused on Ram Shankar, Bhikari Charan, Godabarish, and Ashwini Kumar are significant in this context. Yet, these works do not clarify the distinct trajectory of historical dramas and their impact on the evolution of Odia nationalism.

Bengali and Hindi historical drama segments are superior in both quantity and quality compared to the historical drama segments in Odia literature. Notable contributions to the field of historical drama research include Shakti Bhattacharya's *Bangla Eitihaska Nataka* (1967), Dhananjay's *Hindike Eitihask Natakome Itihas Tatwa* (1970), and P.R. Bhupatkar's texts in Hindi and Marathi that resemble historical dramas. However, these works do not establish solid principles and traditions for the discourse on historical drama.

Evolution of Historical Dramas

Historical drama emphasises literature more than actual historical facts. The story begins at a point where history itself becomes silent, focusing on the complex events that shaped individuals' lives in the past. While the thoughts and feelings of historical figures are often lost in historical accounts, drama delves into the fluctuations of their deepest emotions. As a result, history's unspoken and fragmented nature finds clarity and resolution through drama.

Historical drama combines elements of history and art. While history exists outside the realm of drama, art resides within it. Grounded in historical context, it aims to uncover historical truths. As a literary form, historical drama incorporates both dramatic reality and the essence of eternal life. To reveal these truths, the historical dramatist carefully prepares using historical data to reconstruct the past. After thorough analysis, the dramatist seeks to contextualise history through specific, verifiable facts, conveying the life experiences of that historical period to the audience. Every effort is made to maintain the historical accuracy of the play. Generally, there is often a lack of interest in reading history. However, experiencing

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the captivating stories of the past in a theatre can ignite excitement and curiosity. The playwright takes advantage of this opportunity to create historical dramas. These works have played a crucial role in fostering a sense of national consciousness among the generally illiterate population of Odisha during the colonial era.

The 7th-century drama *Beni Sanhar* by Bhatta Narayan is often overlooked as connected to Odisha.¹ In contrast, Murari Mishra's 9th-century drama *Anargha Raghava* is recognised as the true beginning of theatre in Odisha. Krishna Mishra's drama *Prabhodha Chandrodaya*, from the Ganga period, highlights the courage of the Odia people. During the Gajapati period, works such as Kapilendra Deva's *Parshuram Vijaya*, Rayaramananda's *Jagannath Ballabhav* and Jivadevacharya's *Bhakti Baibabha* were composed in Sanskrit. However, these works did not significantly impact the existing Odia literature.

The Odia population's aspiration to write plays in the provincial language was uncommon until the 19th century. No Odia playwright succeeded in forging a spiritual connection with the insular realm of Sanskrit drama. Raghunath Parichha's drama *Gopinath Ballabhav*, composed during the 1866 Great Famine in Odisha, was esteemed as a significant travelogue.² Although it is a travelogue, it should be acknowledged as the foundation for dramatic creativity. Jaganmohan Lala's play *Babaji*, authored in 1877, attained recognition as the first significant drama in Odia literature.

Two newspapers founded in Odisha at that time highlighted 'that dramas like *Babaji*'s had yet to be written in the Odia language. Although it did not represent a genuine drama comparable to English or Sanskrit dramas, it was the first drama book published in the Odia language.'³

Gourishankar Ray and Fakir Mohan Senapati launched a significant initiative for the Odia language in 1869, promoting public awareness for its preservation. During this time, Ram Shankar Ray wrote a drama titled *Kanchi Kaveri*, which was recognised as a nationalist work and positively impacted the theatrical scene in Odisha.⁴ Historical records indicate that in 1911, the play *Kanchi Kaveri* was fervently staged at Satyabadi High School, facilitated by Pandit Gopabandhu Das.⁵ At that time, this historical drama epitomized the former splendour of Odisha and contributed to the emergence of nationalism. Dr. Sukumar Sen stated that, at that time, history encompassed folklore and tales. Consequently, history and folklore were

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intertwined in *Kanchi Kaveri*, and the historical component cannot be evaluated as lesser or greater.⁶

In the early 20th century, Bhikari Charan's plays *Kataka Bijaya* and *Raja Purusottam Dev* displayed limited nationalist themes. The play *Kataka Bijaya* is based on the events of the British conquest of Odisha and its capital Cuttack in 1803.⁷ It depicts the moral and psychological misery of the people of Odisha under the Maratha rule.⁸ It is believed to have been written based on Toynbee's *History of Odisha* (1874) and Jagmohan Lal's *Odisha Vijaya* (1876).⁹ Radhamhon Rajendra Dev, the king of Chikiti, authored and performed in the play *Sri Pratap*, which drew inspiration from the famous Bengali play *Rana Pratap Singh* by Dwijendra Lal Ray. Following Ram Shankar Ray, Godabarish was crucial in promoting nationalism among the Odias. His works, including *Purusottam Dev* and *Mukund Dev*, were more literary than theatrical but contributed significantly to the rise of nationalism.¹⁰ Contemporary playwright Gobind Chandra Shuradeksha further enriched the historical play tradition in Odisha with works such as *Mukund Dev*, *Mewar Putra*, *Utkal Ramani*, and *Hindo Vijaya*. Despite numerous performances, his dramas did not capture their deserved attention.¹¹

National consciousness primarily drives the advancement of historical drama. While artistic ideals and the structure of the stage influence it, various events related to national awareness have added to its richness. This connection between the phases of national consciousness reveals their intrinsic and symbolic links and their distinctions from state ideals.

Dr. Tarachand has compared India's intellectual renaissance and reformation efforts to overcome colonial oppression to a theatrical performance. "The first part of this play starts following the Battle of Plassey and concludes its final scene on August 15, 1947. This monumental drama shares essential elements of ethical conflict and authentic power struggles. The prologue is rooted in ancient history, but the events unfold in the eighteenth century. The play is presented in three acts. The first act depicts the erosion of liberty due to India's moral degradation. The second act illustrates a resurgence of energy within the Indian psyche, fueled by the influence of a foreign civilisation that revitalises India's ancient essence. Finally, the third act reveals India's journey toward self-awareness and its triumphant march toward emancipation."¹²

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The character of national consciousness and the liberation movement in Odisha is unique. The region has endured long struggles for regional autonomy against its neighbours and has sought to achieve independent status through various movements. Consequently, the phases of Odisha's national consciousness do not easily fit into a universal context. Dr Tarachand believes that Odisha's decline is due to rigid attitudes and illiteracy rather than efforts to eradicate languages and dialects, which is the focus of the first act. The second act shows signs of self-interest and celebrates progress. Odisha's narrative becomes more closely aligned with universal themes by the third act. The drama culminates in conflicts stemming from Odisha's quest for provincial recognition, evolving into a broader liberation movement in the final act.

The analysis of Odia's historical drama unfolds in distinct and impactful phases. Each phase reveals the depth and richness of the narrative, capturing the audience's attention and enriching their understanding of history. The following phases are outlined below.

- (a) Ram Shankar and the evolution of consciousness concerning historical plays
- (b) The contributions rendered by Bhikari Charan
- (c) Godabarish and the Emergence of Odia Nationalism
- (d) Ashwini Kumar and the development of nationalism
- (e) Contribution of other dramatists in the growth of Odia historical dramas.
- (f) Liberation from provincialism and the advancement of nationalism
- (g) Independence and self-emancipation of unacknowledged heritage

The development of historical dramas and their contribution to the growth of nationalism during the colonial period can be broken down into several phases, including the expansion of historical dramas between the years 1880 and 1915, the dramas written between 1915 and 1936, and the dramas produced between 1936 and 1947.

Historical Dramas from 1880 to 1915

Ram Shankar Ray illustrated the historical upheaval in Odisha during the 19th century in his inaugural play, *Kanchi Kaveri*. His characters embodied the Utkal spirit, reflecting his role as a leader in the Hindu revival movement. However, he did not abandon the reform of the Bhakti religion. This blend of influences shaped him into a harmonist, similar to the development seen in Bhikari Charan. He had a different approach to nationalism. He

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criticised the Odias' pride in their historical legacy, which he viewed as stagnant. His goal was to establish a new Utkal based on an alternative trajectory.

Neither Ram Shankar's nor Bhikari Charan's plays explicitly or implicitly challenge British rule. Many of Bhikari Charan's plays predominantly praise the British. Nationalism in the 19th century was not about achieving freedom but aimed at reform. The revivalists of Hindu India had a specific goal, which led them to commend the British openly.

In a speech in London in 1870, Keshav Chandra Sen, a leader of the Brahma Samaj, remarked, "England arrived by divine will and came to India, proclaiming, 'Arise, my sister! You have been in slumber for a long time.'"¹³ The esteemed poet Rabindranath Tagore echoed this sentiment: "We began the struggle for our nation's freedom, yet a deep faith in the goodwill of the British nation resided within every heart. This faith was so strong that our sages believed that the liberation of this oppressed nation would come solely through the kindness of the victorious country."¹⁴ Historically, England was seen as a refuge for the oppressed. Pandit Nehru described this period as the festival of Hindu resurgence, noting, "The initial wave of Indian nationalism in the nineteenth century was primarily religious, particularly focused on Hinduism."¹⁵

1. Several textbooks on Pan-Indian History were produced in Odisha between 1880 and 1915. However, these works did not include original research on the subject; instead, they focused primarily on the history of Odisha. As a result, nearly all the dramas from this era are rooted in the region's history, with *Sri Pratap*, composed later, being an exception.
2. The Odia people's historical awareness primarily derived from storytelling, with the *Madala Panji* as a critical source. The plays from this time reveal a lack of understanding of authentic history. Nevertheless, the uncertainty surrounding these events is minimised in *Kataka Bijaya* since they are based on distant historical events.
3. Religion played an intrinsic role in shaping historical consciousness during this period. The Hindu awakening in the early nineteenth century fostered a trend of interpreting the *Puranas* as historical accounts. This intertwining of mythology and history is evident in theatrical performances, with *Kanchi Kaveri* and *Chaitanya Lila* serving as prime examples. In contrast, *Bhikari Charan* lacks this religious sentiment.

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4. Ram Shankar has provided a rich narrative of Odisha's past, while Bhikari Charan portrays Odisha's decline and supports British rule. They present divergent perspectives on Odisha's reconstruction.
 5. The reformist national movement emerged alongside the language movement in Odisha, facilitating the region's unification and adding significant value to the dramas of that time. However, the depth of national awareness is often not clearly articulated, as it frequently reflects other sentiments.
 6. Most plays from this period are semi-historical, drawing inspiration from folklore, mythology, and national sentiment. Each play vividly depicts man's greatness, presenting men as the primary agents of hard work and progress. Given men's predominant role in political history, their representation is often normative, resulting in female characters being portrayed as marginalised and peripheral. *Padma's* character in *Cuttack Vijay* exemplifies this tendency.
 7. During this time, protagonists and other typical play characters were often depicted as national heroes. This hero worship led to a focus on only the most prominent characteristics of these figures.
 8. While many plays did not emulate English drama, Sanskrit drama heavily influenced them. The presentation of topics through *Nandi Natanati* and the concluding reflect this adherence to Sanskrit tradition.

Historical drama from 1915 to 1936

The national consciousness of the nineteenth century was ignited across India by the partition of the Bengal movement. Following the formation of the Utkal Conference, Odisha nationalism began to flourish in the region. Madhusudan Das, a key figure in this movement, stated at the Utkal Conference, "The head is situated in one location, the hands in another, and the feet in yet another. This condition cannot be deemed a healthy state for an individual. Just as a tide is essential to consolidate all reservoirs, a national tide must be generated universally to unify our country."¹⁶

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The associates of *Satyabadi* played a significant role in elevating Madhusudan Das's vision. While their ultimate goal was pan-Indian nationalism, achieving independence for Odisha was the initial priority. Gopabandhu noted in an editorial for *Satyabadi* in 1818 that "the organisation primarily addressed matters concerning Odisha and the Odia language. Now, some space has been created for political issues in India. Odisha has numerous faults, concerns, and challenges. Its position in India cannot be determined until these issues are resolved. Still, it is essential to recognise that it is an integral part of a broader India, sharing its joys and sorrows to some extent."¹⁷

Godabarish was the inaugural dramatist of fervent Utkal nationalism. The sentiment-driven drama's comprehensive and robust manifestation emerged in Ashwani Kumar's historical plays. Pandit Krupasindhu, a member of *Satyabadi*, was a pioneer in nationalist historiography. His works, including *Utkal History*, *Barabati Durga*, and *Konark*, vividly showcased Odisha's historical grandeur. During this era, several historical texts were published, including Tarini Charan Rath's *Ghumsar Itihas* (1913), Mukunda Das's *Kalapahad* (1921), Rakhal Das Banerjee's *Odisha Itihas* (1930-31), Godabarish Mahapatra's *Kapilendra Dev* (1930), Akshay Kumar Chakravarthy's *Odisha Itihas* (1934), and Chakradhar Mahapatra's *Rodhang Itihas* (1936). These works were instrumental in establishing the golden age of Odisha's historical drama. Pandit Godabarish Mishra's contributions to drama during this period laid the foundation for Utkal national consciousness. However, in terms of artistic methodology, the leading dramatist of this era was Ashwini Kumar Ghosh. His plays are celebrated for their intense nationalist sentiments and exceptional qualities. Ashwini Kumar's role in elevating Odisha's historical drama to new heights is unforgettable.

The eminent playwright Ashwini Kumar, along with his contemporaries Balkrishna Kar, Ramaranjan Mohanty, Kalandi Charan Panigrahi, Kaliprasana Kavi, Seemadri Patnaik, Lala Nagendra Kumar Ray, Dhaneshwar Das, Karthik Kumar Ghosh, and Nikunj Kishore Das, gained recognition between 1915 and 1936. They successfully crafted historical dramas that drew upon intriguing material from the histories of Odisha and India. Their illustrious plays, such as *Chandragupta*, *Gaud Vijeta*, *Priyadarshi*, *Aviram Singh*, *Kalinga Vijaya*, *Kharvela*,

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and *Mir Kashim*, despite their imaginative richness, depicted the political and socioeconomic conditions of India and Odisha during that era.

Ashwini Kumar, the most renowned playwright of this period, authored 35 plays. His works, including *Saoji* (1918), *Kalapahad* (1922), *Govinda Vidyadhar* (1922), *Keshari Ganga* (1925), *Konark* (1927), *Utkal Gourav* (1932), *Samaleswari* (1931), and *Kapilendra Dev* (1935), deeply resonated with the Odia audience, leading to his significant popularity.

Another notable playwright, Kalicharan Patnaik, primarily focused on social themes, using contemporary events in his social theatre to influence his historical tragedies. His finest historical drama is *Avijan* and *Raktamandar*. Several playwrights have written plays based on Indian history, inspired by the theme of universal love. Notable works from this period include Balakrishna Kar's *Chandragupta* and Kalandi Charan Panigrahi's *Priyadarshi*, which were crafted in a nationalistic style.

Seemadri Patnaik of Parlakhemundi is a prominent contemporary drama writer renowned for his many historical plays alongside Kalicharan. His historical dramas, including *Prithviraj*, *Anangabhima Dev*, *Veerashree Chudaganga Dev*, *Veerashree Kapilendra Dev*, *Sri Pataparudra Santrata*, *Kharavela Aira*, *Yayati Keshari*, *Utkal Chandrodaya* and *Narayana Dev* are all rooted in Odia nationalist ideals. The play *Veerashree Anangabhima Deva* first premiered in the name of *Jayadeva* at the famous Odisha theatre Padmanabh Rangalaya in Parlakhemundi in 1929. Before the play's publication, Kalicharan's play *Jayadeva* was published, leading to the renaming of the play to *Anangabhima Dev*.¹⁸

Nikunj Kishore's play *Kapilendra Dev* captures the essence of Kashia-Kapila mythology. In contrast, although Mayadhar Mansingh gained notable recognition as a poet, his plays *Budha*, and *Barabati* often fail to engage audiences. The drama *Barabati* is a nationalist literary piece, and its narrative and dialogue reflect Odia nationalism. The play's final scene reveals Anangabhima Dev's rhetoric, highlighting Mansingh's deep commitment to nationalism. Mansingh places greater emphasis on Odia nationalism than on all-India nationalism.¹⁹

1. As awareness of contemporary education and ideology grew, dramatic content increased. National enthusiasm shifted away from mythology, religious practices, and the extraordinary elements of historical drama, leading to the evolution of drama as a secular art form.

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2. Drama has taken shape through illustrious legends and historical narratives. Ashwini Kumar has authored brief historical dramas such as *Paikapua*, *Odia Jhia*, *Samaleswari*, *Keshari Gang*, and *Taj Mahal*.
 3. Dramatists have adapted historical narratives to align with national consciousness throughout the evolution of plays. It is evident in several works, including *Purushottam Dev* and *Mukunda Dev* by Godabarish Mishra. The plays by Ashwini Kumar's play *Govinda Vidyadhar* exemplify this genre.
 4. Since the beginning of women's awakening in India, women have taken on prominent roles similar to male characters in theatrical performances. This can be seen in *Odia Jhia*, *Keshari Gang*, and *Tarabai*.
 5. As many plays are based on events, external conflict has become a focal point, leading to a noticeable absence of internal conflict.
 6. There has been a significant emphasis on robust dialogue synthesis in these plays. The dialogues reflect contemporary ideas, and dramatic preferences suggest that the conversations are uplifting and infused with national sentiment. Notable plays that exemplify these qualities include *Konark*, *Kalapahad*, *Kalinga Vijaya*, *Gaud Vijeta*, and the two plays written by Godabarish.
 7. After 1921, Odisha's theatre experienced significant transformations. Previously, the lack of a permanent stage limited playwrights' ability to experiment with their writing. As a result, Bengali dramas were performed in many professional and amateur theatres throughout Odisha for an extended period. The establishment of the Radhakrishna Theatre marked a pivotal moment in the composition and performance of historical dramas in Odisha, primarily due to Ashwani Kumar's remarkable historical plays.

Drama from 1936 to 1947

Following its establishment as a distinct state in 1936, Odisha has fervently contributed to the nationwide liberation struggle. The Odia national identity has expanded beyond Odisha to encompass Indian nationalism. Consequently, Odia playwrights have focused on them, and

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the heroic narratives of Odisha's national heroes and those recognised throughout India have been depicted in the plays.

1. The inclination to create historical biographical plays has been particularly evident during this period. Kavichandra Kalicharan's dramas, inspired by the lives of eminent figures such as *Jayadeva*, *Sarala Das*, *Atibadi Jagannath Das*, and others, represent the national pride of Odia.
2. Odisha's and India's history have significantly influenced the play's choice of subject matter. The altered national consciousness is exclusively accountable for selecting such topic matter.

Here is a table listing the dramatists, their plays, and the publication years.²⁰

SL NO	NAME OF THE DRAMA	NAME OF THE DRAMATIST	YEAR
01	Kanchi Kaveri	Ram Shankar Rai	1881
02	Chaitanya Lila	Ram Shankar Rai	1906
03	Bhatru Sneha	Bikram Dev Verma	1909
04	<i>Kataka Bijaya</i>	Bhikari Charan Pattnaik	1909
05	Praraprudra	Parbati Charan Das	1913
06	Nandikeswari	Bhikari Charan Pattnaik	1915
07	Sri Pratap	Radhamohan Rajendra Dev	1916
08	Purusottam Deva	Godabarish Mishra	1917
09	Mukunda Deva	Godabarish Mishra	1918
10	Seoji	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1918
11	Kalapahada	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1922
12	Raja Purusottam Deva	Bhikari Charan Pattnaik	1924
13	Samaleswari	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1924
14	Amara Sinha	Brundabana Bihari Das	1925
15	Keshari Ganga	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1925
16	Chandra Gupta	Balakrishna Kar	1926
17	Mahuri Patana	Krupasindhu Patadeva	1926

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18	Konark	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1927
19	Abhihrama Sinha	Kali Prasana Kabi	1929
20	Abhiram Sinha	Bijaya Pratap Singhdeo	1929
21	Gouda Vijeta	Ramaranjan Mohnaty	1931
22	Jyotsna Bai	Durga Prasad Deva	1932
23	Kharavela	Dhaneswar Das	1932
24	Utkal Gourav	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1932
25	Priyadarshi, Padmini	Kalandi Charan Panigrahi	1933
26	Tajmahal	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1933
27	Paika Pua	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1933
28	Salabega	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1934
29	Bhanja Bhujanga	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1936
30	Odia Jhia	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1936
31	Gobinda Bidyadhara	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1937
32	Tarabai	Ananta Prasad Panda	1937
33	Kalinga Sinha	Chudamani Nayak	1938
34	Mir Qasim	Kartik Kumar Ghosh	1938
35	Prithviraj	Simhadri Pattnaik	1938
36	Buddha Charita	Bikram Dev Verma	1941
37	Mewar Putra, Mukunda Dev, Utkala Ramani, Hindola Vijaya	Gobinda Chandra Surdeo	1930 to 1939
38	Kalinga Vijaya	Lala Nagendra Kumar Ray	1945
39	Jaydeva	Kalandicharan Pattnaik	1946
40	Avijan	Kalandicharan Pattnaik	1946
41	Rathore Rani	Kali Prasana Kabi	1947
42	Atibadi Jagannath Das	Kalandicharan Pattnaik	1948
43	Kabisamrat Upendra Bhanja	Manoranjan Das	1949

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44	Kabi Surya	Ramchandra Mishra	1949
45	Bhanjakabi	Debendra Kumara Singha	1950
46	Sesha Swadhinata	Lala Nagendra Kumar Ray	1950
47	Barabati	Mayadhara Mansingh	1951
48	Buxi Jagabandhu	Manoranjan Das	1951
49	Rakta Mandar	Kalandicharan Pattnaik	1952
50	Buddha	Mayadhara Mansingh	1952
51	Gajapati	Sadasiv Nanda	1952
52	Kabi Gopalkrushna	Narasimha Mahapatra	1953
53	Kapilendra Deva	Aswini Kumar Ghosh	1953
54	Kabi Samrat	Rajat Kumar Kar	1953
55	Sarala Das	Kalandicharan Pattnaik	1954
56	Chinnangi	Parsuram Harichandan	1954
57	Sahid Bajirout	Banchhanidhi Routray	1955
58	Begam Kothi	Suren Mohanty	1957
59	Virasri Anangabhima Deva	Simhadri Pattnaik	1957
60	Surendra Sai	Prabhat Mukherjee	1957
61	Kapilendra Deva, Kharavela	Nikunja Kishore Das	1958
62	Goutam Buddha	Nikunja Kishore Das	1958
63	Mahapurusha	Gopinath Mohanty	1958
64	Rajnartaki	Bhanjakishor Pattnaik	1959
65	Prataprudra	Bhanjakishor Pattnaik	1959
66	Digvijaya Kapilendra	Parsuram Harichandan	1961
67	Surya Mandira	Jadunath Dashmahapatra	1962
68	Dalabehera	Gopal Chhotray	1966
69	Surendra Sai	Rajat Kumar Kar	1968
70	Akhanda Jyoti	Byamokesh Tripathy	1970
71	Biplabi Krutibasa	Parsuram Harichandan	1970

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72	Chandan Hujuri	Rajat Kumar Kar	1970
73	Abhisapta Durga	Parsuram Harichandan	1978
74	Bhimadeva, Bira Chudanga Deva, Birasri Kapilendra Deva, Sri Prataprudra, Kravela Ayra, Jajati Keshar Utkala Nandodaya, Narayan Deva	Simhadri Pattnaik	1920-1958
75	Kapilendra Dev	Dhandeswar Das	
76	Kharavela, Kapilendra Dev	Satyanarayan Rajguru	
77	Nandikeswari	Bira Kishor Ray	
78	Utkal Vijeta, Prithviraj	Satyanarayan Panda	

Conclusion

Bengali drama prominently features the theme of liberation, with notable works such as *Palasira Paryashchit*, *Maharaj Nandakumar*, and *Tupu Sultan*. After India gained independence, many plays were written that highlighted the experiences of Indian persecution under British rule and expressed the anti-British sentiments prevalent among the people of Odisha. Manoranjan's play *Buxi Jagbandhu* vividly depicts the tyranny faced by the Khurda people during the Pika Rebellion. Pankajkishore Pattnaik's subsequent works, *Prataparudra* and *Rajnartaki*, have also gained considerable popularity. In the post-independence period, several prominent historical dramatists, including Ramchandra Mishra, Gopal Chottaray, Devendranath Singh, Nilkanth Pattnaik, Suren Mohanty, Rajat Kumar Kar, Byomkesh Tripathi, Parshuram Harichandan, Banchhanidhi Routray, Shraddhakar Supkar, and Yadunath Das Mahapatra, have introduced innovative perspectives to historical drama.

Nearly all renowned Odia historical dramas, such as Ram Shankar's *Kanchi Kaveri*, Godabarisha's *Mukunda Dev* and *Purushottam Dev*, Ashwinikumar's *Konark*, *Kalapahad*, *Utkal Gourav*, Govinda Vidyadhar, Kalicharan's *Abhiyan*, Manasingha's *Barabati*, *Buxi Jagabandhu* by Manoranjan, Bhanjkishore's *Prataparudra*, Gopal Chottray's *Dalabehera*, and Rajat Kumar's *Surendra Sai*, are derived from the history of Odisha. Many of these

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narratives provide intricate accounts of the triumphs and defiance of the emperors of the Utkal Empire. The purpose of these plays is to evoke a resurgence of consciousness among the Odia populace by recalling historical grandeur. After 1920, the plays *Kharavela* and *Kapilendra Dev*, authored by dramatist Dhaneshwar Das, highlighted the concept of Odia nationalism and Odia soldier's bravery.²¹ The Patna Rajendra Narayan Dramatic Association first staged these works in 1930. The plays commend Utkal's heroism, art, and culture in a vibrant and impromptu manner, which significantly contributed to the formation of nationalism in Odisha. Notable works in this category include Ashwani Kumar's *Bhanj Bhujang*, *Paika Pua*, *Odia Jhia*, *Balangi*, and Kalicharan's *Rakta Mandar*. *Kalinga Vijaya*, authored by Lala Nagendra Kumar Ray, is a prominent historical drama from Odisha and received the Kalahandi Award for being the premier play in the state. This play is based on Ashoka's deep regret and conversion to Buddhism after his conquest of Kalinga.²² *Gaud Vijeta*, written by dramatist Ramaranjan Mohanty, significantly contributed to the rise of nationalism in Odisha. According to literary professor Kalandicharan Panigrahi's introductory address, this play was successfully staged by performers from Ravenshaw College in 1931—the drama centres on the story of Pratap Rudra Dev's victory over Bengal. Historical dramas in the Odia language have portrayed the struggle of the Indian populace against British rule in the post-independence era. This period saw the emergence of a robust foundation of nationalism and deep self-reflection. The tone in the works of playwrights such as *Buxi Jagabandhu*, *Surendra Sai*, and *Begum Kothi* is compelling. The dramas *Buxi Jagabandhu*, *Biplabi Krittivas*, and *Surendra Sai* were composed after India gained independence. Some plays emphasise regional history. While the content is well-organized, engaging, and enjoyable, these plays have made a lasting impact on readers and audiences.

Notes and References

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